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FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG WORKING WOMEN - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALORE CITY

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Abstract :

Financial literacy is closely connected to an individual's emotional, personal, social, economic, and employment success. An individual needs to understand the basics of money management, and use financial resources appropriately to function well in society at a personal, professional, business and community level. Financial literacy enables the people to access, effectively use and derive maximum benefit from financial services. This is a continuing process by which individuals improve their understanding of financial products, concepts and risks develop skills and confidence to be more aware of financial risks and opportunities to make informed choices. There is a vast segment of population in India who suffer from lack of financial literacy in terms of utilizing their own money and also safe and secure place to avail savings, credit, insurance and remittances .Financial literacy enables people to know, understand and also to estimate the future risk and return associated with the financial products and make responsible decisions. Financial literacy is needed for maintaining the financial stability of the country.

Keywords: financial literacy, investment avenues, government.

1. Introduction:

Financial literacy is the skill, knowledge and information which an individual acquires in order to make effective judgement to manage financial resources and financial well-being of his future. Globalization resulted in introduction of many new financial products which are unique, profitable and also risk oriented. To make a qualitative decision regarding these financial products an individual must be financially literate. Women are a vital part of the Indian Economy, both at the national and the household levels. They make one-third of the national labour force. Indian women contribute a much larger share of their earnings to basic family maintenance with the result that women's earnings positively and immediately affect the incidence and the security of poverty. Availability of credit is made very simple and easy for individuals but if individuals fail to understand the terms and conditions on which credit is made available, and then they may end up entering into debt trap. Therefore understanding the concepts of financial literacy has become the need of an hour. Financially literate individuals are able to improve their quality of life that is they will be in a better position to sail through toughest financial times by having diversified investments, insurance cover, and savings. Financial literacy enables people to know, understand and also to estimate the future risk and return associated with the financial products and make responsible decisions.

Definitions:

¹NFER defines Financial Literacy as, ‘the ability to make informed judgements and to make effective decisions regarding the use and management of money’.

²PACFL defines the term Financial Literacy as ‘the ability to use knowledge and skills to manage financial resources effectively for a lifetime of financial well-being.

2. Review of literature:

Hussein A. Hassan³³ (2009) in his study states that financial literacy of UAE investors is below the needed level. The study analyses the relationship between the financial literacy and the influence of the factors that affect the investment decisions. The study found that a significant difference in the level of financial literacy was found between the respondents according to their gender. Women were found to have lower level of financial literacy than men.

Lusardi et.al; (2010) in their study made an attempt to understand the factors that contribute for acquisition of financial knowledge. Influence of parents on youngsters in gaining financial knowledge is also highlighted. Study was conducted with an objective to know level of financial literacy youngsters have and the main factors contributing to acquisition of financial knowledge. The study revealed that parent’s education especially mothers education directly contributes for gaining financial literacy. Study suggested that parents should educate their children on financial concepts and products so that in future they can gain complete knowledge of financial products which will help in their saving and investment.

Saritha (2012) made an attempt to study the level of advanced financial literacy which working women of Punjab possessed and observed that the younger women have already developed the plan for investment. Working women invest their money in insurance plans as they are not willing to take risk to earn profit and want to have a safe future. Overall level of financial literacy among women of Punjab is average.

Jiyane and Zawada (2013) made an attempt to determine money management behaviour and utilisation of financial products of informal sector women entrepreneurs in South Africa. The study revealed that eradicating poverty through financial literacy will result in economic development of a country. The level of financial literacy among the selected sample members was very poor than estimated.

Nurul and Saleh (2013) conducted an exploratory study in Malaysia to examine how financial literacy influences individual savings in modern market. The main objective was to examine the dependency of financial literacy on individuals saving behavior. Results of demographic profile of respondents show that financial literacy of aged people is higher than because of long term investments than younger people. The study observes that the respondents have very good knowledge on basic financial literacy concepts and knowledge on advanced financial literacy concepts was low. Majority of the respondents are aware about risk diversification. Study suggests conducting more programs on financial education.

Javed Iqbal Bhabha (2014) made an attempt to assess the financial literacy and its impact on saving-investment behaviour of working women in Pakistan. The working women though possess better understanding about basic financial concepts but they lack knowledge about advanced financial concepts. From the study it is examined that working-women in Pakistan are financially illiterate. One of the biggest problems, with working women in developing

¹ National Foundation for Educational Research

² President’s Advisory Council on Financial Literacy, 2008 – Annual report (executive summary)

countries like Pakistan, is that they do not treat Personal Finance as something that's important for them. For ages, they have not participated in Personal finance, regarding it as the man's area. Study suggests that saving-investment behavior depends on their financial literacy.

Abdul Haque and Zulfiqar (2016) studied the impact of financial literacy, financial attitude and financial wellbeing on economic empowerment of working women. The main objective of the study was, to measure the level of financial literacy and awareness of financial products among 300 working women of Pakistan. It was observed from the study that working women even after having good knowledge of financial products and good source of income, showed very low interest towards investment. Study suggested for improving and building positive financial attitude for working women on investment and savings. Financial wellbeing was the most influencing factor among all other selected factors.

Nishitha and Neerja (2016) conducted a descriptive and analytical study taking a sample of 200 respondents. The study makes an attempt to find out the saving and investing behavior of newly employed youth. Major findings are level of financial literacy among the respondents are same but they differ in selection of investment avenues. Female respondents give more importance to budget and they find investing in stock market difficult and usually prefer to save in commercial bank or post office products. Respondents have good theoretical knowledge financial products and returns but practically they fail in application of their knowledge.

Anshika and Anju Singh (2017) opined that the level of financial literacy in India is very poor. The level of financial literacy prevailing in India will not result in further economic growth. The study suggested conducting seminars, workshops, other awareness programmes to target groups in order to give them practical knowledge of financial aspects and also to collect feedback on such activities conducted.

Chetna and Raj (2017) conducted a study on, 'Financial literacy among women – Indian scenario with an objective to understand and evaluate the level of financial literacy among women in developing country like India. Women are financial experts, they are good in budgeting and managing cash but when it comes to taking big financial decisions they turn back and leave it to their spouses or other male members. Women lack confidence to take financial decisions and are always dependent on Men. Education, financial problems, socio-cultural barriers and physical barriers are some of the reasons for low level of literacy among women. Study also highlighted the efforts taken up by RBI with other financial institutions to improve financial literacy among individuals in India.

3. Objectives of the study:

- To study the degree of financial literacy among the working women.
- To study the obstacles faced by women in gaining financial knowledge.
- To suggest measures to improve the financial literacy of working women.

4. Significance of the Study:

Financial literacy is the basic requirement to promote financial inclusion. In India, the need for financial education is even greater considering the low level of literacy and the large section of the population, which is still out of the formal financial set-up. The Reserve Bank of India has undertaken a project titled "Project Financial Literacy" with an objective to disseminate information regarding the central bank and general banking concepts. Commercial Banks have come up with a link on its web site for the common person to give

the ease of access to information. A few banks have taken initiatives to start some centers in rural/ semi urban areas, which offer financial education and credit counselling services. It will also benefit the financially-included by helping them make informed choices about the products and services available in the market to their best advantage.

5. **Research Methodology:**

The study was conducted through descriptive survey methods using both primary and secondary data. Questionnaire was distributed randomly to 100 working women. Secondary data were collected from various books, journals, websites, and newspapers.

6. **Results and discussions:**

- Majority (46%) of respondents belong to age group of 30-40 years and 90% are working for a private company.
- 60% of respondent's monthly salary ranges from 20000-40000 and 80% of respondents are married.
- 64% of respondents have completed their graduation and 20% post-graduation. Respondent's education qualification is good which shows that they have knowledge about basic financial products.
- 42% of respondent's have savings up to Rs.8000 per month and their source of information to save is bank officials and friends.
- 21% of respondents have De-mat account. This may be because most of the women are comparatively not ready to face any kind of risk. They usually think about safer investment.
- Majority (40%) of respondents prefer to invest in jewellery, 16% in recurring deposit, 16% in mutual funds, 4% in real estate, 14% post office products and 10% in fixed deposit. This result proves that women are aware about modern financial products but because the risk factor is more they go for traditional investments.
- 34% of respondents are aware and have child life policy and 32% have opted for term policy.
- Majority (72%) of respondents are ready to face low risk in relation to their investment.

7. **Suggestions**

Women earn income and also save a major share of income but they opt only for risk free or less risky investment. Overall financial literacy among women is moderate. They are aware of all modern financial products but lack confidence to practically use those avenues. Therefore women should be given proper training to make use of modern financial products by conducting workshops, seminars, guest talks.

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